

OBSERVATION REPORT

**Observation Report of
Gloria Bilingual Christian School's STEAM's Fair 2025**

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8 April 2025

Abstract

STEAM learning is one of the many efforts in the field of education to keep up with societal changes. Educational institutions are required to change dynamically and adaptively within increasingly shorter timeframes compared to previous eras. In this report, the author conducted an observation of STEAM learning at Gloria Christian Bilingual School, located on Banjar Sugihan Street, Tandes, Surabaya, through the GBCS STEAM Fair 2025. This observation focused on two main questions: (1) What are the potentials and weaknesses of the 2025 GBCS STEAM Fair event? and (2) What aspects of STEAM learning at GBCS can be improved? Based on the SWOT analysis results, the author identified several weaknesses in the STEAM learning implementation, including the fact that project-based learning still appeared to be more product-oriented, and digital technology/AI-based components were not yet present in the fair. In response to this, and grounded in literature review, the author suggests that the school reflect on its current approach to Project-Based x STEAM learning and proposes the design thinking approach as a fresh perspective. Additionally, the author offers several engaging activity ideas that consider strong selling points and better academic quality for future implementation. It is hoped that STEAM learning at Gloria will become even more excellent and a leading force in future STEAM Fairs.

Keywords: Gloria school, STEAM, PjBL, Design Thinking.

Observation Report of GBCS's STEAM's Fair 2025

The observation was conducted during the STEAM Fair event on Tuesday, March 25, 2025, at Gloria Christian Bilingual School, located on Banjar Sugihan Street, Tandes, Surabaya. The purpose of this observation was to assess the performance and potential of STEAM learning through the 2025 GBCS STEAM Fair activities. This report will address two main points:

- (1) What are the potentials and weaknesses of the 2025 GBCS STEAM Fair event?
- (2) What aspects of STEAM learning at GBCS can be improved?

SWOT Analysis of GBCS' STEAM Fair 2025

At the fair, there were around 30 booths showcasing students' projects. The STEAM projects were generally categorized into mechanical, electrical, chemical-based, and hydro-powered types. The participating students were from Grades 1 to 3 of Gloria's schools. The event was held in a semi-outdoor hall that included a small stage. From the hall, visitors could access the school's open area and play zone, which were also filled with various natural elements to explore. Based on the observer's experience, the following is an analysis of Gloria STEAM's learning, drawn from the observation of GBCS' STEAM Fair 2025.

STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adopt international curriculum - Openness to global perspectives - Well resources & facilities - Good & strategic locations - Big Community: Strong in values and numbers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product Based = (x) PjBL - Digital Technology/ AI based learning hasn't showed up - The Fair's audience is minimal
OPPORTUNITY	THREAT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well known as a school with Student Centered approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School with Coding/ robotics program

- Leading as STEAM based School

- Gloria STEAM isn't that special (as selling point)

Aspects could be improved at GCBS' STEAM Learning

Gloria Schools have a strong sense of community, rooted in Christian values. Their reputation as an educational institution is well established in Surabaya. With a growing community in both size and quality, there are several aspects of their STEAM learning that could be further developed. These areas of improvement represent potential opportunities to help the schools continue evolving in alignment with the changing demands of society, particularly within the context of Smart Society 5.0.

STEAM Learning

What is STEAM? STEAM is widely used and implemented in education around the world (Mercan & Kandır, 2022). It began as **STEM**, an initiative emphasizing the importance of interdisciplinary learning to improve education in the United States, introduced in 1993 by the United States' National Science Foundation (NSF). In 2019, STEM evolved into a standalone discipline aimed at integrating the four core fields. However, there is still no universal consensus on how STEM should be viewed globally (Tawbush, Stanley, Campbell, & Webb, 2020).

In **India**, STEM education is conceptual due to limited access to science and technology resources. In **Italy**, STEM tends to focus more on three disciplines: mathematics, science, and technology. Meanwhile, in **Singapore**, although STEM is widely adopted as a curriculum, its implementation lacks uniformity. Data shows that STEM functions either as a formative assessment format for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) programs or as a "playmaker" initiative. However, many STEM documents in Singapore tend to focus more on technology and mathematics (Tawbush et al., 2020).

Whereas, on **July 31, 2018**, in the United States under President Trump's administration, **architecture, computer science, and coding** were designated as part of STEM. This is stated in Statute 132

Public Law 115-224 of the 115th Congress, published by the House – Education and the Workforce and the Senate – Health, Education, Labor, and Pensions Committee (Thompson, 2019). This shows that STEM continues to be researched and remains relevant today.

STEAM is not much different from STEM; its main focus is the integration of interdisciplinary fields. In the 21st century, STEM has also evolved in Europe through various forms of practice and implementation. In **2011**, NextGen criticized that to truly innovate and enhance economic potential, education still needs the **Arts**. Since then, the term **STEAM** has gained popularity among practitioners and educators. STEAM is considered to have a positive impact on critical thinking skills and social awareness (Chappell & Hetherington, 2024).

In Taiwan, STEAM learning focuses on developing computational thinking (CT) and design thinking (DT). In 2014, Taiwan's Ministry of Education emphasized the importance of mastering skills in two technological domains: information technology and living technology. The core of information technology is CT, and the core of living technology is DT. Meanwhile, literacy-oriented (LO) skills help students adapt to the future world. A PLS-SEM study in Taiwan revealed that CT has a significant direct impact on STEAM and LO; DT directly influences STEAM, and STEAM has a significant direct impact on LO (Hsu, Chang, Chen, Tsai, & Yu, 2023).

Other Learning Instruments Could be Improved?

Learning Strategies: Project Based Learning. Project-Based Learning is a **student-centered** approach and a development of inquiry-based learning. In this model, students begin learning by addressing questions derived from real-life case studies, ultimately leading to meaningful learning (Kokotsaki, Menzies, & Wiggins, 2016). The concept of meaningful learning can also be found in the definition of **mindful learning**, which is a learning process involving higher-order thinking (Wang, 2010).

Project-Based Learning is highly recommended in learning that relates to science and innovation. Students with strong scientific skills have greater potential for real-world problem-solving. The challenge

lies in comprehensive readiness—on the part of teachers, institutions, and students. Students need good **self-efficacy**, support from authorities, and teachers who are well-versed in project-based learning. Additionally, implementing PjBL requires a longer process. One solution is to apply **micro-project-based learning** (Darmilah, Rochintaniawati, & Rafikah Agustin, 2023).

The integration of STEM and project-based learning can enhance **ICT literacy** and **problem-solving skills**. Through STEM-PjBL, students undergo a cycle of designing, creating, testing, and redesigning a product in groups. This process enriches ideas and boosts creativity (Darmilah et al., 2023). Successful PjBL depends on the teacher's ability to **scaffold motivation, support, and guidance** throughout the learning process, which helps reduce **cognitive load** (Kokotsaki et al., 2016).

Three key points of PjBL were identified by Cocco (2006) in (Kokotsaki et al., 2016), student **engagement** in the learning process, students achieving learning objectives through **social interaction**, and students being able to **share their knowledge and understanding**. Furthermore, the PjBL process is characterized by student **independence, constructivist inquiry, goal-setting, collaboration, communication, and reflection** on real-world issues (Kokotsaki et al., 2016).

Figure: Steps of PjBL model (Jalinus, Nabawi, & Mardin, 2017)

Learning Method: Design Thinking Approach. **Design Thinking** is a mindset. This way of thinking is *human-centered, collaborative, optimistic, and experimental* (Riverdale & IDEO, 2011). Design Thinking opens up possibilities for students, showing that solutions may not only come from a single option or may even take unexpected forms.

Design Thinking differentiates itself from other types of problem solving, such as:

- Solving problems that already have structured and known solutions (e.g., volcano eruption demonstrations),

- Completing mathematical problems,
- Or solving closed-ended engineering challenges.

Instead, Design Thinking offers a range of possible solutions, such as:

- Developing technologies or products,
- Improving structures or communication systems,
- Creating and designing physical spaces (classrooms, schools, playgrounds, parks, etc.),
- Applying knowledge into design (e.g., math for architecture, science for medical protocols, engineering for emergency shelters, history for new policies),
- Creating artistic projects (artworks, music, dance, fashion, etc.),
- Writing and producing works (deepening character, alternative storylines, fiction, fantasy, etc.)

(Goldman & Zieleski, 2021)

In general, Design Thinking includes the following phases:

1. **Discovery**
2. **Interpretation**
3. **Ideation**
4. **Experimentation**
5. **Evolution**

(Riverdale & IDEO, 2011)

Figure: Phases of Design Thinking (Riverdale & IDEO, 2011).

In learning processes specifically, Design Thinking consists of four phases:

1. Exploring the problem space
2. Empathizing
3. Brainstorming
4. Prototyping and testing cycles

(Goldman & Zielezinski, 2021)

Performance-Based Learning. To optimize STEAM learning, a **performance-based assessment** approach can also be applied. This kind of assessment not only measures complex cognitive abilities but can also serve as a guide for developing learning experiences.

Below are **guiding questions** that can be used to design performance-based learning:

- a. What factual knowledge or concepts are important for students to understand?
- b. What intellectual skills will be achieved when this knowledge is applied?
- c. What thinking habits do students need in order to successfully apply this knowledge?
- d. What character traits, ways of thinking, or values are typically held by individuals who succeed in academic environments?
- e. What mental characteristics or personal qualities are common among professionals such as scientists, writers, journalists, historians, mathematicians, or musicians?
- f. What signs or indicators can I observe to show that students are beginning to develop those traits or mindsets?
- g. What social skills are needed for someone to collaborate and succeed in professions like journalist, weather presenter, park ranger, historian, economist, or mechanic?
- h. What kind of evidence would convince parents that their child has developed these skills?
- i. How are real-world practices in math, history, science, art, writing, and other fields carried out by professionals in their daily lives?
- j. What kinds of projects or assignments are typically completed by professionals and could be adapted into school learning experiences?
- k. What roles or mindsets do professionals in these fields possess that can be nurtured in students in the classroom?
- l. What are the most important characteristics that show a high degree of a specific trait?
- m. What types of mistakes are acceptable for a lower score?
- n. What kinds of constraints genuinely mirror those encountered by real-world performers?
- o. What kinds of constraints bring out the best in novice performers and creators?
- p. What authentic limits should be placed on access to the six previously listed resources?

(Kubiszyn & Borich, 2013)

Event Suggestions

Considering all of the above, the author proposes several potential STEAM Fair activities and a fresh perspective in packaging the STEAM Fair. Instead of holding the event as a one-time showcase, it can be distributed into **thematic micro-events**, such as:

a. **Movie Festival**

Students can present short documentary or historical films as a way to express opinions or raise awareness about specific issues.

b. **Night Gala**

The school can host a gala night to showcase visual art or musical performances, accompanied by a dinner involving all school members and parents.

c. **Math and Science Fair**

Students can present the results of their experiments conducted over a set period of time.

d. **Summer Camp, Art Gallery, Techno Fair, etc.**

Final Word

The **Gloria community** has promising resources and potential. Especially with the presence of Gloria Bilingual Christian School, which prioritizes **STEAM** and an **international curriculum**, the school is well-positioned to bring a unique identity to the broader Gloria community and stand out among other schools in Surabaya.

The **STEAM Fair** should not merely be a showcase of beautiful products, but rather the result of **students' higher-order thinking processes**. Therefore, the author recommends that the school reflect on its current implementation of STEAM learning, reconsidering old habits and evaluating its Project-Based Learning approach.

By doing so, future school events and exhibitions can become more **diverse and open-ended**, with strong **academic quality and high selling points**. Realizing this vision will require **well-planned scheduling** and **comprehensive collaboration** across the entire Gloria community.

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